

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory Pilot Implementation

HerStory Map Excursion Guidelines for Athens (Greece)

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cooperativus societas entus

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1. Introduction

The current document is developed to provide guidelines on tour excursion development, for monuments of women in local history and to ensure that the experience is educational, engaging, and respectful, a set of best approaches is presented below, to select the most suitable for each country.

The first phase of excursion will take place at a pilot phase with 160 persons in total (at least in the pilot excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and at least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. Following to the excursion, all partners will collect the feedback, make the necessary changes, and then prepare another excursion, the final one.

Final excursion will involve 160 persons in total (at least in the excursion), so **20 people from each country**, and least half of the total (**10**) **must be Young people**. At the end a total of 320 participants (as a minimum), at least half of the total (160) must be young people.

The participants of the excursions will consist of young people and educators, trainers and academics:

- young people, boys, and girls
- young people active in local community groups such as Municipalities' Youth Councils
- students from the fields of History
- students from the fields of Gender Studies
- youth experts
- youth organizations
- Academics from the fields of History and Gender Studies
- Teachers and educators
- Teachers, and women and human rights organizations experts/activists

Each partner will create different and specific activities for the excursions organized in their city, for the pilots and the final ones. A set of general guidelines are presented below and each partner will analyse and formulate the topics of the guidelines with additions in the excursion descriptions, based on each country specifics.

The target audience for the tour guide guidelines is:

- A. touristic offices and educators.
- B. Small groups (independent excursions)

Regarding KEAN-Kyttaro Enallaktikon Anazitiseon Neon and Athens/Greece, fourteen monuments/historical places dedicated to women are included in the map. As Athens is a big capital, these points are not necessarily in walking distance. So it is proposed to organize either mini-tours depending on the distance of these monuments between them or to

organize a big tour via bus or other kind of transportation. For piloting, a mini-tour that includes five monuments dedicated to women within walking distance seems preferable.

After meeting at the starting point a brief description about the tour is necessary and before visiting each monument questions about it should be introduced, including in that way an interactive element.

While the original tour is designed for 20 people, it can be adapted to a larger number of participants, depending on the number of the separate tours that would be implemented.

2. Guidelines to develop a physical excursion

LEVEL 1: How to create a unique tour

1. Define Objectives:

- **General Objective:**

To highlight the women who have made significant contributions to the history of Athens and Greece through an educational experience developed within the city.

- **Specific objectives**

- To conduct a city tour, visiting locations that showcase the contributions of notable women.
- To organize either separate mini-tours or a comprehensive tour, tailored to the number of participants, their interests, and profiles.
- To encourage collaboration among participants from both groups involved in the tour.
- To promote cultural interest in learning about the influential women of Athens.
- To enhance the representation and visibility of Greek women in historical narratives and public discourse, ensuring their stories are acknowledged and valued.
- To assess the effectiveness of the activity through recorded observations.

2. Define the thematic of the excursion:

The thematic of the excursion is based on the target audience and can range from presenting important women in the history and development of Athens and Greece in general, through different positions and in different fields to specific fields of action. This will be achieved through visiting monuments or historical places dedicated to women that tend to be ignored.

When forming the visiting groups, we should aim for diversity in profiles, including students, stakeholders, adults, and intergenerational groups, among others. This approach enables a more comprehensive understanding of how different individuals interact during such activities.

3. Recommend a rich educational content for each woman presented:

LOCATION NUMBER	1
LOCATION	Bookstore "Colourful Planet"
WOMAN	Marina Galanou
INFORMATION	<p>Marina Galanou had been President of the Greek Transgender Support Association, publisher of the publishing house and bookstore "Colourful Planet", and was with civil society organizations for more than 20 years. Founding member of the Transvestite - Transsexual Solidarity Association (SATTE) and General Secretary from 2003 to July 2014. General Secretary of the Greek Homosexual Community (G.H.C) from 2006 to 2008. Founding Member and President of the Greek Transgender Support Association (GTSA). She had been a Council of Europe Expert on sexual orientation and gender identity and participates in this capacity as a trainer in training seminars for Hellenic Police officers, asylum officers, magistrates, judges and prosecutors, as well as being a member of the legislative preparatory committee for legislation on legal recognition of gender identity.</p> <p>She is the author of two books, "Gender Identity and expression. Definitions, Stereotypes, Myths and Discriminations" and "I am trans - I know my rights", a columnist in print and electronic media, and has worked extensively in all areas of fundamental human rights and freedoms.</p> <p>Appointed by the National Commission on Human Rights as a full member of the National Council Against Racism and Intolerance in November 2019.</p> <p>Marina opened roads. he has been instrumental in trans visibility, helping many trans boys and girls break through fear and assert their place in society. She wrote books, took part in speeches, was a member of institutional bodies, such as the National Council against Racism and Intolerance, had</p>

	been an expert of the Council of Europe on issues of sexual orientation and gender identity, but above all you could find her on the streets of the struggle for human rights and freedoms.
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LOCATION NUMBER	2
LOCATION	Pedio tou Areos-Bust of Manto Mavrogenous
WOMAN	Manto Mavrogenous
INFORMATION	<p>Manto Mavrogenous' bust was made in 1937 and is located in Pedio tou Areos. It is one of the 21 busts that are dedicated to the Greek heroes of the Greek War of Independence (1821). Manto Mavrogenous (1796- 1840) was a Greek heroine of the Greek War of Independence (1821), that contributed her fortune for the Hellenic cause. She was born in Trieste by an aristocratic family, but her origin was from Mykonos, where she led the rebellion of the island's inhabitants against the Turks. With ships, two equipped with her own money, she pursued the pirates who were ravaging the Cyclades and then fought in Pelion, Fthiotida and Livadia. Manto Mavrogenous' financial support of the Struggle and her general activities, such as her letters to the philhellenic women of France and England, made her name legendary in European philhellenic circles. For her overall contribution to the War, she was honoured by Ioannis Kapodistrias with the rank of Lieutenant General. Later she was persecuted and exiled by the politician Ioannis Kolettis and eventually died penniless in Paros, as she had spent her entire fortune on the struggle.</p>

LOCATION NUMBER	3
LOCATION	Pedio tou Areos-Bust of Domna Visvizi
WOMAN	Domna Visvizi

<p>INFORMATION</p>	<p>Domna Visvizi (1783–1850) was a Greek maritime captain who fought in the Greek War of Independence. At the outbreak of the war, Visvizi joined her husband Chatzi Antonis Visvizis to fight for the Greek cause onboard the ship Kalomoira. After her husband was killed in battle in July 1822, Visvizi took command of the ship and continued to fight in the war. Among other contributions, Visvizi aided in the Greek capture of the island of Euboea. After running low on funds and being rejected additional funding by the Greek leadership, Visvizi gave over the Kalomoira to the Greek navy in 1824. After the war she was left destitute and with next to no government support lived in poverty until her death in 1850.</p>
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<p>LOCATION NUMBER</p>	<p>4</p>
<p>LOCATION</p>	<p>Pedio tou Areos-Bust of Laskarina Bouboulina</p>
<p>WOMAN</p>	<p>Laskarina Bouboulina</p>
<p>INFORMATION</p>	<p>Bouboulina was born in Constantinople in 1771. Her father was Stavrianos Pinotsis, an Arvanite from Hydra and her mother was Skevo Kokkini, descendant of the Byzantine Kokkinis family. During her youth, she developed an interest in sailing which was facilitated by her stepfather's liberal attitude to education. She was widowed twice, inheriting a considerable sum of money from her second husband. She later allegedly joined the Filiki Etaireia secret society which sought to achieve Greek independence from the Ottoman Empire, being among the few women to do so. Following the outbreak of the Greek War of Independence she commanded a fleet of Spetsiot ships which contributed to several campaigns most notably the siege of Nafplion. Following the defeat of her faction in the Greek civil war in 1824, Bouboulina was</p>

	briefly imprisoned and expelled to Spetses. She was killed on 22 May 1825, during the course of a family feud.
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LOCATION NUMBER	5
LOCATION	Exarheia Square-Lela’s Karagianni Bust
WOMAN	Lela Karagianni
INFORMATION	<p>Lela Karagianni's bust in Exarcheia square was made in 1958, funded by the Association of Greek Women Scientists. Lela Karagianni (1898- 1944) was a legendary fighter of the National Resistance against the German troops in the period 1941- 1944. A protagonist of the «Secret War», although a mother of seven children, she was the first Greek citizen to offer organized resistance against the German enemy. She created the organization named “Bouboulina”, funded by herself. She was imprisoned (with her five children) and executed by the Germans troops. She became a renowned symbol of resistance worldwide. After her death, she was awarded the Award for Virtue and Self Sacrifice by the Academy of Athens and, in 2011, the honorary title of the Law of Nations by Yad Vashem, the Foundation for the Memory of Martyrs and Heroes, while in 2020 she was awarded the honorary rank of Brigadier General. Today, there is a marble bust of her in Exarcheia square in Athens. Also, her house and base of her resistance movement in Plateia Amerikis is considered to be a historical monument that needs special protection.</p>

LOCATION NUMBER	6
LOCATION	Paxinos-Minotis Museum
WOMAN	Katina Paxinou

<p>INFORMATION</p>	<p>The Paxinou-Minotis Museum is a museum in Athens that is devoted to the Greek film and stage actress Katina Paxinou (1900-1973). Katina Paxinou was born in Pireaus and she was one of the founding members of the Greek National Theatre. She was the first Greek actress who managed to make it in Hollywood and even on her own terms, to excel in theatre and cinema in Europe and to stand out as a tragedienne of global importance. She was the first non American actress that won an Academy Award for Best Actress for her performance in the film "For Whom the Bell Tolls". She played in numerous performances of the National Theatre of Greece. She died of cancer in 1973 and is justly considered as the greatest Greek actress of the 20th century. Her husband, the director Alexis Minotis, created a museum in her memory, that after his own death, was named Paxinos Minotis Museum. The Museum and Archive are housed in the Eynardos Mansion, 20 Agios Konstantinos St. and 52 Menandrou Street, in the centre of Athens.</p>
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<p>LOCATION NUMBER</p>	<p>7</p>
<p>LOCATION</p>	<p>Marble Plaque of Antigoni Krontira-Metaxa</p>
<p>WOMAN</p>	<p>Antigoni Krontira-Metaxa</p>
<p>INFORMATION</p>	<p>This plaque was placed in honor of the educator Antigoni Metaxa - Krontira or "Aunt Lena" after the naming of this green space. The choice of this particular area as "Aunt Lena's Garden" was made because there is a kindergarten in the same area and it is adjacent to the "Elena Venizelos" Maternity Hospital. Antigoni Metaxa-Krontira (1905-1971) was an important Greek educator. She studied Educational Science in Paris and Acting at the Drama School of the Athens Conservatory. In 1933 she founded the first children's theatre for children in Greece. She was the author of 54 children's books, including the six volume children's encyclopedia and the Encyclopedia of Greek Mythology for children. She produced vinyl records of fairy tales and songs</p>

	and the first children's television show. Her goal was to educate children by entertaining them. For all her work she was awarded by the Academy of Athens.
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LOCATION NUMBER	8
LOCATION	Tzeni Karezi's Theatre
WOMAN	Tzeni Karezi
INFORMATION	Tzeni Karezi's Theatre was build in 1978 by Tzeni Karezi and her husband (also an actor) Kostas Kazakos, in order to host their theatre company. Tzeni Karezi (1932- 1992) was an important Greek actress, with rich social and political activity. She came from a conservative family, that didn't allow her that job career. She went against her family wishes and she studied in the Drama School of National Theatre. She managed to be a protagonist in important plays in cinema and theatre. During the Greek Junta in 1967 -1974 was exiled for playing in a theatrical play with resistance messages. She was one of the most commercial and highest paid names in Greece. She died in 1992, due to cancer. In 1992 the foundation "Tzeni Karezi "was created, that offers palliative care for free in cancer patients.

LOCATION NUMBER	9
LOCATION	National Gallery
WOMAN	Opi Zouni

INFORMATION	<p>Greek National Gallery was build in 1900 in Athens. It hosts more than 15000 paintings. Opi Zouni's paintings are some of the few that belong to greek women artists. Opi Zouni (1941-2008) was an important Greek painter and artist born in Kairo, with origin from Crete and Santorini. She studied in Greece, in School of Fine Arts. Due to her gender, she could not present her work in Greece. She has held over 70 solo exhibitions in Europe and 450 participations in group exhibitions. She was a representative of geometric art in Greece. Her creations were influenced by Arabic culture but also incorporated Greek elements. Unfortunately, in our country her work wasn't recognized at her time because she was a woman. Today, a lot of her paintings can be found in Greek National Gallery in Athens.</p>
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LOCATION NUMBER	10
LOCATION	Experimental Special Primary School "Rosa Imvrioti"
WOMAN	Rosa Imvrioti
INFORMATION	<p>This Special Primary School is named by Roza Imvrioti. Roza Imvrioti (1898-1977) was a Greek educator, a pioneer of special education, with a rich social and political activity. She worked as a teacher of literature in middle schools and in 1934 she became the first female middle school principal. She founded the first Experimental Special Primary School in Athens (1937), the first official effort in Greece for the systematic education of children with mental difficulties. Today, this school is still named by her name to pay tribute to her contribution and work in the field of special education and can be found in Kaisariani, Athens. She was an elected member of the Council of the International Women's Union. She was exiled and suffered tortures due to her political activity.</p>

LOCATION NUMBER	11
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LOCATION	1st Cemetery of Athens- Calliroe Parren's Bust
WOMAN	Calliroe Parren
INFORMATION	<p>On June 6, 1992, more than fifty years after her death, Callirroe Parren was honoured by the Hellenic Republic with the unveiling of her bust at the First Cemetery of Athens. Kalliroi PAREN (1861-1940) is considered to be one of the first Greek feminists. She also claims the title of the first Greek woman journalist, editor and director of the newspaper "Efimeris ton Kirion". It was written exclusively by women and addressed mainly to women in Athens and Piraeus. This newspaper continued to be published for almost thirty years until 1918 when Callirroe was exiled to Hydra for her political beliefs. The aim of the newspaper was to introduce in Greece the feminist concerns that were already preoccupying women in Western European countries and to awaken the consciousness of the women of the time. She had had a rich social and political activity, represented Greece in a lot of international conferences and was exiled for the political views. Through her own action, Greek government allowed to women to be able to study in the University.</p>
LOCATION NUMBER	12
LOCATION	1st Cemetery of Athens- Sofia Vembo's Grave
WOMAN	Sofia Vembo
INFORMATION	<p>Efi Bembou, known professionally as Sofia Vembo, was a leading Greek singer and actress active from the interwar period to the early postwar years and the 1950s. She became best known for her performance of patriotic songs during the Greco-Italian War, when she was dubbed the "Songstress of Victory"</p>

LOCATION NUMBER	13
LOCATION	Plaka-Melina Mercouri's Bust

WOMAN	Melina Mercouri
INFORMATION	<p>Melina Mercouri's bust was build in 1999 and is located in Plaka, Athens. Melina Mercouri (1895- 1967) is represented in middle age. She was a charismatic personality and one of the most important Greek women of the 20th century. She was described as "the last Greek goddess" and a woman of flame. She was distinguished as an actress, by playing in theatrical plays and movies that won international awards. She also left her mark as a politician with her fight against the dictatorship, but also with her interventions at international level as Minister of Culture. She initiated the fight for the return of Parthenon Marbles back in Greece, a fight that still continues. Today, there is also a cultural foundation in her memorial that can be found in Polignotou 11, centre of Athens.</p>

LOCATION NUMBER	14
LOCATION	Onassis Cultural Foundation- Sappho's Statue
WOMAN	Sappho's Statue
INFORMATION	<p>The statue of Sappho in Athens was made by Antoine Bourdelle and is located in Onassis Foundation. Sappho (~ 630 - 570 BC), was a Greek lyric poet from Lesbos, particularly well known from antiquity to the present day.</p> <p>Sappho wrote love poems, hymns to the gods and epithalamia (wedding songs). Her poetry vibrated with spontaneity and intense emotions. Little is known about her life. It is likely that she was born in Eresos, Lesbos. She was a contemporary of Alcaeus and Pittacus. She was born to an aristocratic family on the island of Lesbos during a great cultural blooming in the area. When the aristocracy of the island was driven into exile from Mytilene due to political unrest, Sappho fled to Sicily. Later, after the fall of tyranny, she returned to Lesbos and gathered around her young women from the aristocracy of the island and the cities of</p>

	<p>Asia Minor to teach them the arts of music and poetry, in the service of Aphrodite and the Muses. The philosopher Maximus of Tyre (2nd half of the 2nd century AD) describes her as small and dark-haired. She was considered to be homosexual, and that identification accompanies the poet to this day. In modern times, lesbian love has also been associated with her name. After her death, a coin was minted in Lesbos in her image, statues of her were erected in Syracuse and Pergamum, and a cenotaph was built in Syracuse in her memory. It is possible that many of her works were lost due to their not being copied, perhaps because of their low demand after the rise of Christianity and a stricter view of morality.</p>
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4. Define a compelling excursion tour content:

Complementary materials will be selected to display, such as photographs of the locations, photographs of the women, readable texts, etc.

1. Marina Galanou

2. Manto Mavrogenous

3. Domna Visvizi

4. Laskarina Bouboulina

5. Lela Karagianni

6. Katina Paxinou

7. Antigoni Metaxa-Krontira

8. Tzeni Karezi

9. Opi Zouni

10. Rosa Invrioti

11. Kalliroi Parren

12. Melina Mercouri

12. Sofia Vembo

13. Sappho

5. Tour Excursion Planning

Athens is a big city with long distances from an area to the other. HERSTORY monuments are spread across the whole city, therefore transportation is needed in the case of visiting all monuments. The tours can be tailored based on various aspects as presented below, covering the target audiences needs:

- Thematic: Selection of monuments based on the theme: art, science, history, all women
- Season: during summer months from June – September, the temperatures are quite high in the city center, therefore is recommended to implement short tours either early in the morning or late at the evening, also eliminating walking distances
- Distance in klm: focusing on specific areas or covering the distance with transportation

For HERSTORY pilot tour excursions, a two-hour tour was organized, focusing on the area of Kypseli towards city center. During the tour the audience visited monuments representing important women from various fields. The tour started at the “Colorful Panet” bookstore, sharing the story of Marina Galanou an activist for transgender rights. The next stop was in ‘Pedion of Areos’, sharing the story of three heroines in Greek revolutionary war and the last stop was at the bust of Lela Karagianni.

LEVEL 2: Guidelines to develop a physical excursion: How to implement an exciting tour

1. Add Interactive Elements to excursion tour:

A treasure hunt mobile application is being developed through the HerStory project and will create an interactive experience at the tour locations. The treasure hunt consists of a series of questions that can be posed at different points during the tour, such as before visiting a particular site. This presents an excellent opportunity to remind participants about these notable figures and ask related questions, thereby enhancing interactivity and creating stronger mental connections between the locations. You can download the app at HERSTORY map: <https://map.herstoryproject.eu/>

Additional to the treasure hunt, we have designed a series of questions intended to foster discussions during the tour and inspire curiosity about women's impact on the history of various cities among the participants.

Questions:

City, Country: Athens, Greece		
Number	Treasure Hunt Point	Content for treasure map
1	Melina Merkouri's bust	Mention one more information that you know for Melina Merkouri.
2	Tzeni Karezi's Theatre	Can you name one more famous movies that she has been a protagonist?
3	Sappho's Statue-Cultural Foundation	Are you aware of any other woman in ancient Greece?
4	Manto Mavrogenous' Bust Domna Visvizi's' Bust Laskarina Bouboulina's Bust -Pedion tou Areos	Have you heard about these women heroines before? From where?
7	Paxinos-Minotis Museum	Are you aware of any other movies she has played in?
8	Marble Plaque of Antigoni Krontira-Metaxa	Did you know her work? From where?
9	National Gallery-Opi Zouni	Are you aware of any other women artists at that period?
10	Experimental Special Primary School "Rosa Imvrioti"	Did you know her work? From where?
11	Lela Karagianni's Bust-Exarxeia Square	Do you know any other monuments linked to Lela Karagianni?

12	Kalliroi Parren's Bust-1st Cemetery of Athens	Do you know any other feminist magazine and any feminist organisation?
13	Marina Galanou	Do you know any other organisation for the rights of transgender people and LGBTQI community?
14	Sofia Vembo	Do you know any song from the artist?

2. Accessibility

All of the suggested points are accessible and reachable. Nevertheless, accessibility in Athens has become a significant issue in recent years due to limited application of accessibility measures at the effort of a city to become more inclusive and accessible for all residents and visitors, including people with disabilities. That leads to the conclusion that people with disabilities might face serious issues while trying to reach the points, including transportation or obstacles in front of ramps.

Regarding the accessibility of information, various means of visual and audio systems will be offered to support all participants in the excursion tour experience, for example audio guides iPad screens, microphones and various translation options will be available.

3. Receive Feedback and Improvement

After completing the tour/mini-tours participants will be invited to fill out the [HerStory questionnaire](#) to provide valuable feedback (this can be modified based on tour-guide specifics). This will give them the opportunity to share suggestions for improvement, comments, questions, or concerns about the excursion. The feedback collected will help make any necessary improvements to enhance future experiences and provide data on participant involvement and satisfaction with the activity.

Additionally, reminders will be sent in the days following the tour to encourage participants to respond to the questionnaire using the email address provided during registration. Furthermore, the European Commission survey will be utilized for the project purposes.

4. Locals through Collaborations:

The collaboration with local historians, institutes, experts, or community leaders who can provide insights into the historical and cultural context of each monument is recommended for some locations, to increase the engagement throughout the tour.

Here we recommend specific organisations that can provide more information on monuments or can add value to the tour excursions related to women empowerment.

Organisation	Information
Polychromos Planitis	Publishing house and Bookstore created by Marina Galanou and her Partner. The co-owner shared information about Marina Galanou.
Transgender Support Association	The association that supports transgender people’s rights, also founded by Marina Galanou.
Lean In	Is an organization supporting girls and women to achieve their goals through empowerment and mentoring.
Women Act	Women Act is a non-profit non-partisan organization that aims at empowering women in fulfilling their political, social, cultural and economic potential by generating knowledge, providing training and connecting with the civil society.
Panteion University	Functions of Sociology, of Political Science, of Communication and Culture.

LEVEL 3: Generic guidelines for individual and self-guided tours

1. Enable the customization of excursions:

The tours can be tailored based on the period and the target audience specifications. Emphasis could be given in different monuments depending on national holidays, festivals or even achievements. For example, a thematic tour could be organized in 28th of October, which is the National Holiday for celebrating the Greek resistance during World War II. A mini tour dedicated to the women that participated in the resistance could be organized.

2. Develop options for Training Guides or/and self-guided tours:

- Develop a brochure, including the locations of all the respective monuments/historic places associated with women that contributed to the city/country. Also, it can include educational information and pictures for each woman. Here is the template that can be used for Greece: <https://www.canva.com/design/DAGSPCUC74o/Vu3QbloUZQzAGliejHq5FA/edit>

- Use a questionnaire that includes questions about the history/contributions of each woman via an interactive platform.
- Establish potential mini-tours, starting and ending points.
- Involve tour guides that are well prepared and educated about the content.

Extra tips

Having a QRCode printed to go to the local map of the city, so people can follow the tour or access to the guidelines to make the tour in an educational way.